

Unveiling the shift from proton-coupled to hydride-coupled electron transfer and its origin

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ABSTRACT

This study explores hydride-coupled electron transfer (HCET) as an alternative mechanism to canonical proton-coupled electron transfer (PCET). HCET was identified in the reaction between a $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complex and various organic substrates, involving hydride transfer coupled with electron transfer from $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ to the substrate in a single-barrier step. First, we identified the connection between the thermodynamic cycles and reactivity and show that the mechanism – whether HCET or PCET – is dictated by the cycle with more favorable off-diagonal thermodynamics. The distinction between the mechanisms is evidenced by correlation with electronic structure-based descriptors derived from atoms-in-molecule charges and volumes. In HCET, the hydrogen atom gains electron density and volume at transition state indicating hydride character, while in PCET, it loses electron density and volume signaling proton character. Second, intrinsic bond orbital analysis confirmed that HCET is a two-electron process (opposing to one-electron PCET): it involves the complete transfer of the proton and the C–H α -electron from substrate to the Cu ion while the β -electron undergoes a transient exchange, initially migrating to the Cu center before returning to substrate. The presented HCET mechanism is compared with the hydroxyl group transfer pathway, in which the corresponding anion/electron transfer involves three separate electrons.

Introduction

Proton-coupled electron transfers (PCETs) are vital to life, driving essential processes such as energy conversion in the mitochondrial respiratory chain and photosynthesis.^[1-4] In mitochondria, PCET facilitates proton transfer across the inner membrane, creating a proton gradient crucial for ATP synthesis.^[5,6] In photosynthesis, it enables the light-driven splitting of water into oxygen, protons, and electrons, providing the reducing power needed for carbon fixation.^[7]

PCET also underpins enzymatic catalysis, enabling key biochemical transformations. For example, nitrogenase enzymes use PCET to reduce atmospheric nitrogen to ammonia in nitrogen fixation,^[8] while hydrogenases catalyze the interconversion of protons and molecular hydrogen in hydrogen evolution, pivotal for microbial metabolism and energy storage.^[9-11] These examples highlight central role of PCET in energy conversion, redox balance, and life-sustaining biochemical transformations.

In synthetic chemistry, PCET has become essential for advancing the synthesis of natural and pharmaceutical compounds.^[12-17] It enables selective C–H bond activation, a transformative approach for constructing complex molecular architectures. Direct C–H functionalization via PCET mechanisms offers efficient strategies for assembling sophisticated molecules with exceptional step- and atom-economy.^[18-20] For instance, the selective C–H oxidation of the terpene sclareolide provides a streamlined, scalable route to derivatives of this potent anticancer adjuvant.^[21]

From a theoretical standpoint, PCET involves two weakly coupled transfers — of an electron and a proton — that occur simultaneously in a single step, overcoming a single energy barrier. Kinetics of this process is affected by the free energy of the reaction dictated by the relative

energy of the product and the reactant (diagonal states) but also by the energetics of electron transfer (ET) and proton transfer (PT) states – the so-called off-diagonal states (**Figure 1**). These off-diagonal states are associated with the two-step ET-then-PT and PT-then-ET connections of the diagonal states, and were demonstrated to co-affect the height of the PCET free energy barrier.^[22,23] As illustrated in **Figure 1A** (from the middle to the left plot), the more elevated the energy of the ET and PT states, the higher is the free energy barrier for PCET, and conversely – the larger disproportion between the two states, the lower the barrier (from the middle to the right plot). This behavior is quantified by two composite quantities – frustration and asynchronicity, respectively. The former slows down the reaction, whereas the latter makes it faster. Thus, their joint effect contained in the off-diagonal term provides a quantitative insight into the kinetics of the reaction.

A key feature of the reactivity model combining the effect of diagonal and off-diagonal thermodynamics (a so-called three-component thermodynamic model)^[22,23] is its link to the reaction mechanism. This connection was explored on the related example of the radical ligand transfer (RLT) reactions, more precisely, the hydroxyl group transfers.^[24] We found that the RLT mechanism can be classified as either analogous to PCET, i.e. *unidirectional*, where electron and cation OH^+ move together from the OH donor to the OH acceptor (denoted as coupled $\text{OH}_{\rightarrow}^+/e_{\rightarrow}^-$ transfer), or *bidirectional*, with the electron flowing from the OH acceptor to the OH donor, while the anion (OH^-) moves in the opposite direction (denoted as coupled $\text{OH}_{\leftarrow}^-/e_{\leftarrow}^-$ transfer).^[24] Two coupled ion/electron transfer scenarios were shown to be associated with two distinct thermodynamic cycles (**Figure 1B**). Although these cycles share the same diagonal pathway, they differ in their off-diagonal trajectories connecting the reactants and products. As for the cycle for the coupled $\text{OH}_{\rightarrow}^+/e_{\rightarrow}^-$ transfer, each of the two off-diagonals involves two sequential steps: one

pathway begins with OH^+ transfer followed by ET, while the other starts with ET and is followed by OH^+ transfer. In contrast, two off-diagonal pathways in the OH^-/e^- cycle are as follows: one initiated by the transfer of OH^- , followed by counter-directed ET, and the other proceeding in the reverse order. An important result of the study^[24] was that the operative mechanism of the OH radical group (*i.e.*, coupled OH^+/e^- vs. coupled OH^-/e^- transfer) is dictated by the cycle yielding a more favorable off-diagonal thermodynamic effect on the barrier. The findings on radical ligand transfer chemistry prompt an intriguing question: *could an analogous or similar bidirectional mechanism exist in H-atom abstraction reactions? Specifically, is a bidirectional hydride-coupled electron transfer - HCET (H^-/e^-) possible alongside PCET (H^+/e^-)? If yes, might such a mechanism be linked to favorable off-diagonal thermodynamics? What would be a clear electronic-structure signature for HCET vs. PCET? These questions are addressed in the presented work.*

Figure 1. Energetics of the ET and PT states and their effect on the free energy barrier of the PCET reaction in passing from reactant complex (RC) to product complex (PC) through transition state (TS). Energy elevation of the ET and PT states - reflected by larger frustration - increases the PCET barrier (*cf.* left vs. middle plot). Energy disparity between the ET and PT states - reflected

by larger asynchronicity - lowers the PCET barrier (*cf.* right vs. middle plot) (**A**). The full-reaction thermodynamic cycles linked to the two studied hydroxyl ligand transfer mechanisms, *i.e.*, for coupled OH^-/e^- transfer (left) coupled OH^+/e^- transfer (right) (**B**).

Theoretical background

Figure 2 depicts two competing full-reaction thermodynamic cycles that share a common diagonal pathway - thus the same free energy of reaction (ΔG_0) - but they differ in their off-diagonal states, which determine whether the H-atom abstraction (HAA) mechanism proceeds via PCET (*left*) or HCET (*bottom*). Each of these full-reaction cycles is composed of two half-reaction building blocks (in green and red in **Figure 2**), which determine the thermodynamic properties of the two reaction partners, ultimately giving rise to asynchronicity, η and frustration, σ . In case of PCET, both off-diagonal components, η and σ , are composed of free energies of reduction and protonation of X^\bullet and Y^\bullet ($\Delta G_{\text{X}/\text{Y}}^{\text{e}^-}$ and $\Delta G_{\text{X}/\text{Y}}^{\text{H}^+}$, respectively), while η and σ for HCET results from the combination of free energies of reduction and hydride release of/from X-H and Y-H ($\Delta G_{\text{XH}/\text{YH}}^{\text{e}^-}$ and $\Delta G_{\text{XH}/\text{YH}}^{\text{H}^-}$, respectively). The explicit expressions for η and σ associated with PCET and HCET are given in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. The full-reaction thermodynamic cycle for PCET (*left*) and HCET (*right*) between the H-atom donor X–H and the H-atom abstractor Y•. Each of the full-reaction cycles are deconstructed into respective two half-reaction thermodynamic block: one for Y•/Y–H (green arrows) and one for X•/X–H (red arrows). The key energy parameters associated with each half-reaction cycle are as follows: the free energy of one-electron reduction (ΔG^{e^-}) and the free energy of protonation (ΔG^{H^+}) for PCET, and the analogous free energy of one-electron reduction (ΔG^{e^-}) and the free energy of hydride release (ΔG^{H^-}) for HCET. These quantities are used to obtain the composite quantities – asynchronicity η and frustration σ , which are specific to each of the reaction mechanisms.

According to the three-component thermodynamic model,^[22,23] the effect of frustration and asynchronicity on the reaction barrier (ΔG^\ddagger) is then quantified through the equation as follows:

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta G_{00}^\ddagger + \Delta G_{diag}^\ddagger + \Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger = \Delta G_{00}^\ddagger + \frac{\Delta G_0}{2} + \frac{|\sigma| - |\eta|}{4} \quad (1)$$

In this implementation σ and η constitute together a so-called off-diagonal barrier contribution ($\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger \equiv \frac{|\sigma|+|\eta|}{4}$). This term complements the canonical effect of the free energy of reaction ($\Delta G_{diag}^\ddagger \equiv \frac{1}{2}\Delta G_0$), and the non-thermodynamic component to the barrier ΔG_{00}^\ddagger , which is supposed to contain all factors depending on the reaction coordinate in going from the reactant to TS.

While PCET and HCET feature the same barrier contribution ΔG_{diag}^\ddagger , they must be distinct in terms of $\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger$ and ΔG_{00}^\ddagger , the latter of which is usually comparably high/low for the set of related reactions. Thus, the operative reaction mechanism should be dictated by favorable $\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger$ arising from the corresponding thermodynamic cycle from **Figure 2**. This concept is explored and validated in the following sections.

As for the inspection of which mechanism is operative, we applied two independent electronic-structure analyses of transition states of all studied H-atom abstraction reactions. As one approach, we employed the atom-in-molecules (AIM)^[25] method to quantify charges and volumes of the transferred hydrogen atoms at the respective TSs. Specifically, H-atom charge/volume at the TS for the reaction between the C–H bond substrate and the Cu^{II}–OH or Cu^{III}–OH complex (the sub/Cu reaction) was calculated with reference to the arithmetic mean of H-atom charges/volumes at TSs of two respective self-exchange HAA reactions - one between the C–H substrate and its radical form (the sub/sub reaction) and one between the Cu^{II}–OH or Cu^{III}–OH complex and its hydrogenated form Cu^I–OH₂ or Cu^{II}–OH₂ (the Cu/Cu reaction), respectively:

$$\Delta q_{sub/Cu} = q_{sub/Cu}^{TS} - \frac{1}{2}(q_{sub/sub}^{TS} + q_{Cu/Cu}^{TS}) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta V_{sub/Cu} = V_{sub/Cu}^{TS} - \frac{1}{2}(V_{sub/sub}^{TS} + V_{Cu/Cu}^{TS}) \quad (3)$$

The referential q and V quantities calculated for the self-exchange sub/sub and Cu/Cu TSs are included in equations to separate the effects specific to the reaction mechanism (*i.e.*, partial H⁺ or H⁻ formation) from the ones related to the change of the reaction system geometry common to any C–H bond cleavage. Thus, the positive/negative values of $\Delta q_{sub/Cu}$ and $\Delta V_{sub/Cu}$ are then indicative of PCET/HCET mechanism.

Second, we employed intrinsic bond orbital (IBO)^[26,27] calculations to trace the electron flow along the HAA reaction coordinates. As demonstrated by Knizia and Klein, use of IBO analysis allows to differentiate between PCET and H-atom transfer (HAT) mechanism.^[28] In this study, we applied IBO analysis to HAA reactions involving the Cu^{III}–OH and Cu^{II}–OH complexes with selected substrates with the attempt to distinguish HCET from PCET, by associating each of the mechanism with a characteristic evolution of the electrons of the cleaved C–H bond and the OH ligand.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of the candidate systems for HCET vs. PCET in terms of off-diagonal contributions. In search of a system that would support HCET mechanism (*i.e.*, bidirectional coupled H⁻/e⁻ transfer), we focused on the Cu^{III}–OH complex reported by Tolman.^[29-31] The reasons to look into this particular system were as follows. First, this experimentally characterized complex shows high HAA efficiency, however it has a low redox potential, thus suggesting that the reaction might not be driven by ET to the high-valent Cu^{III} site. Additionally, from a computational perspective, the system was previously analyzed using a three-component thermodynamic model assuming the thermodynamic cycle for the PCET mechanism, which produced anomalous results.^[23] Particularly, once the free-energy barrier for abstraction of

hydrogen atom by the $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complex was decomposed into contributions according to eq (1), the corresponding non-thermodynamic part ΔG_{00}^{\ddagger} was found to be negative. Markedly, ΔG_{00}^{\ddagger} , as the equivalent of the intrinsic barrier from the original Marcus barrier model, quantifies the energetic cost of reaching the transition state for the process and, therefore, cannot have a negative value.

Figure 3. The $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}$ complexes and the substrates used in the study, together with the difference between the off-diagonal contributions ($\Delta G_{\text{offdiag}}^{\ddagger}$ from eq (1)) associated with PCET and HCET thermodynamic cycles: negative values indicate preference for the PCET cycle (red), positive – for HCET (blue). For the substrate structures see **Figure S1** in Supporting Information (SI).

In light of this observation, we compared the PCET-derived off-diagonal barrier contribution ($\Delta G_{\text{offdiag}}^{\ddagger}$) for HAA in the $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complex to the corresponding contribution from the alternative thermodynamic cycle associated with HCET, and revealed a remarkable contrast:

$\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger$ for HCET is significantly more favorable than that for PCET (**Figure 3, top**). Moreover, from the mechanistic point of view, the asynchronicity η for HCET reaction favors a hydride transfer over ET. In contrast, when η for PCET is considered, the reaction would be driven by ET, a channel hampered by low redox potential of the Cu site.^[30] This observation partly explains the preference towards the bidirectional coupled H^-/e^- mechanism.

To support findings derived from the three-component thermodynamic model, we strategically modified the system to alter the reaction mechanism. Specifically, we explored the possibility that a one-electron reduced form of $Cu^{III}-OH$ would disfavor hydride transfer, shifting the mechanism to the unidirectional coupled H^+/e^- pathway due to a more favorable $\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger$ (**Figure 3, bottom**). Indeed, the comparison of $\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger$ for the two cycles indicates that the unidirectional pathway is the operative one in case of $Cu^{II}-OH$. Furthermore, such a reaction is driven by PT, as dictated by asynchronicity, which aligns with the high basicity of the $Cu^{II}-OH$ complex reported by Tolman.^[30]

Of note, **Figures S2** and **S3** display the correlation between the reaction barrier (ΔG^\ddagger) and the three-component thermodynamic effect on the barrier ($\Delta G_{diag}^\ddagger + \Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger$ from eq (1)), derived from the correct PCET or HCET thermodynamic cycle, alongside a comparison with the correlation when the thermodynamic effect is taken from the incorrect cycle. For HCET reactions involving $Cu^{III}-OH$, the correlation (R^2) between the reaction barrier and the thermodynamic factor from the HCET thermodynamic cycle is 0.91, whereas the correlation with the thermodynamic factor from the PCET cycle is 0.66. Similarly, for PCET reactions involving $Cu^{II}-OH$, R^2 between the reaction barrier and the thermodynamic factor from the PCET thermodynamic cycle is 0.94, whereas R^2 with the thermodynamic factor from the HCET cycle is 0.82.

Linking HCET and PCET with electronic-structure descriptors. It is reasonable to expect that systems categorized as HCET or PCET based on off-diagonal thermodynamics can also be differentiated using electronic structure-based descriptors at the TS.

In previous work,^[24] we successfully correlated the changes in AIM charge and volume of the hydroxyl group from the reactant complex (RC) to the transition state, providing insights into the mechanism of hydroxyl group transfer reactions. In the full analogy, we can also introduce for the presented HAA reactions the following descriptors:

$$\Delta q_{sub/Cu} = q_{sub/Cu}^{TS} - q_{sub/Cu}^{RC} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta V_{sub/Cu} = V_{sub/Cu}^{TS} - V_{sub/Cu}^{RC} \quad (5)$$

For HAA, however, the RC-to-TS descriptors offer only a slight distinction between PCET and HCET mechanisms. In both cases, these descriptors indicate an increase in charge and a decrease in volume: $\Delta q_{sub/Cu} > 0$ and $\Delta V_{sub/Cu} < 0$, which is consistent with partial H⁺ formation (see **Figure S4**). However, the RC-to-TS change of charge is less pronounced for the HCET reactions, which suggests that the changes related solely to the mechanism of the reaction can be mixed with changes originating from the effects that are common to both mechanisms. In going from RC to PC in both HCET and PCET reactions, when the C–H bond is cleaved and the O–H bond formed, the charge (volume) of the transferred H moiety increases (decreases) from ca. 0.05e⁻ (34 a.u.³) to ~0.6e⁻ (~15 a.u.³). This substantial increase of charge along the reaction coordinate affects also the charge of H atom at the TS, possibly obscuring the mechanism-dependent effects. Of note, the change of charge and volume of the hydroxyl group in OH rebound reaction was visibly less pronounced (0.08e⁻ and 9 a.u.³, respectively) upon the transition from RC to PC, which allowed

to successfully investigate the mechanisms of the reaction using the descriptors from eq (4) and (5). Additionally, the charge of the H-atom is affected by polarization of the C–H bond upon RC-to-TS transition of the substrate geometry, which interferes with the net signature of H moiety transfer was already observed by us in ref 32.

To distinguish the mechanistic signatures specific to a studied reaction from those that are common to all C–H bond cleavage processes, we calculated q and V of the hydrogen moiety at TS with respect to the average of the corresponding q and V values of the two self-exchange reactions - one between the substrate and substrate radical and one between $\text{Cu}^{(n-1)+}\text{-OH}_2$ and $\text{Cu}^{n+}\text{-OH}$ with $n = 2, 3$ (Δq and ΔV from equation (2) and (3), respectively). Indeed, as shown in **Figure 4**, HAA reactions identified as PCET vs. HCET exhibit distinctly different values for the descriptors related to the charge and volume of the transferred H moiety at the TS.

Figure 4. Charge and volume of the transferred H moiety at the TS relative to the referential self-exchange values, as given by equations (2) and (3). The points are colored and shaded from dark blue (favored H^-/e^-) to dark red (favored H^+/e^-) to reflect the difference in off-diagonal thermodynamic contributions to the barrier, which originates from the two different H^-/e^- and H^+/e^- cycles presented in **Figure 2**.

Remarkably, HAA reactions of the $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complex characterized by the off-diagonal contribution favoring the H^-/e^- mechanism form a cluster of points in a single quadrant of the coordinate plane, characterized by a negative value of Δq and a positive value of ΔV . This observed decrease in charge and increase in volume relative to self-exchange reactions indicates that the hydrogen atom gains some electron density. Thus, the hydrogen atom can be distinctly understood as acquiring a partial hydride character at the TS of C–H bond cleavage. In contrast, the points corresponding to HAA reactions of the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}$ complex occupy the opposite quadrant, characterized by a positive and negative value of Δq and ΔV , respectively, which strongly suggests that H-atom develops an electron deficiency at the TS, in line with the protonic character of transferred H moiety in the coupled H^+/e^- mechanism.

Besides the joint effect of asynchronicity and frustration from eq (1) that dictates which of the two H^- or H^+ transfers is operative in the studied HAA reactions, asynchronicity – in terms of both its sign and magnitude, also offers important insights into the extent of imbalance between electron and H^- transfer in HCET, as well as between electron and H^+ transfer in PCET. As the asynchronicity (η) for HCET becomes more positive, hydride transfer is increasingly favored over electron transfer. Conversely, when η becomes more negative, electron transfer becomes increasingly more favored than hydride transfer. In case of PCET, as η becomes more positive, proton transfer is increasingly favored over electron transfer, while a more negative η increasingly favors electron over proton transfer. The Δq descriptor from eq (2) further supports these thermodynamic predictions, revealing that systems with greater asynchronicity in favor of hydride transfer in HCET exhibit a more negative Δq at the TS. On the other hand, the systems more asynchronous in favor of proton transfer in PCET tend to show a more positive Δq at TS. Additionally, the RC-to-TS change of charge from eq (2) allows to capture the same trend, that is

a decrease of charge on transferred H with increasing η in $H_{\rightarrow}^-/e_{\leftarrow}^-$ and increase of charge with increasing η in $H_{\rightarrow}^+/e_{\leftarrow}^-$ (as presented in **Figure S5** in SI).

Intrinsic bond orbital analysis of PCET vs. HCET mechanisms. IBO analysis provides insight into the electron flow along the reaction coordinate^[26,27] and offers a powerful means of distinguishing between HCET (bidirectional $H_{\rightarrow}^-/e_{\leftarrow}^-$) and PCET (unidirectional $H_{\rightarrow}^+/e_{\leftarrow}^-$), further supporting the observations based on off-diagonal thermodynamics and charge/volume-derived descriptors. The IBOs involved in the HAA reactions of both Cu^{II} -OH and Cu^{III} -OH complexes are associated with the α and β IBOs of the C-H σ bond and the α and β IBOs of the O-centered lone pair, as shown in **Figures 5**.

The Cu^{II} -OH-promoted HAA features a pattern well recognized for PCET (**Figure 5A**): the α electron of the C-H σ bond in cyclohexane remains on the carbon atom, while the β electron of the C-H σ bond transfers to the Cu center, reducing Cu^{II} to Cu^I . Concurrently, the oxygen lone pair in the Cu complex accepts the proton, forming an O-H bond. The proton and the electron are accepted by distinct sites, accordingly with PCET reaction.

Unlike the Cu^{II} -OH-promoted PCET, the HAA reaction performed by Cu^{III} -OH exhibits a unique, more complex pattern, where both of the C-H bond electrons participate in the reaction (**Figure 5B**). More specifically, the α - and β -electron at the TS (or in some cases, just prior to reaching the TS) delocalize between the Cu center and the substrate. Subsequently, as the system proceeds along the post-TS reaction coordinate, one of the electrons (α in **Figure 5B**) advances towards the Cu site, while the other (β in **Figure 5B**) re-localizes/returns to its initial position on the substrate. The proton of the C-H bond is accepted by the oxygen lone pair, thus completing the net transfer of a hydrogen, consistent with the expected outcome of the reaction.

In this scenario, the second C–H electron undergoes a bidirectional transfer, initially migrating to the metal complex before being returned to the carbon atom. This process can be described as a bidirectional coupled H^-/e^- transfer, where a proton (H^+) and two electrons — equivalent to an H^- ion — are transiently transferred from the C–H σ bond of cyclohexane to the Cu complex and one electron (the same C–H electron) shifts back to the cyclohexane. This pattern is consistent across all reactions involving $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complex

Additionally, the transient transfer of H^- equivalent between the reactants can be linked to positive values of asynchronicity, which indicate that the favored component of the driving force for the reaction is indeed a hydride transfer and, consequently, that this process will be more advanced at the transition state.

Figure 5. Ion-coupled electron transfer reaction between cyclohexane with the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}$ oxidant (A) and with the $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ (B) along with the associated (i) potential energy profile along the intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) and with the TS in the inset, and (ii) the key IBOs involved in the $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II/III}}\text{-OH}:\text{substrate}]$ reactions. The IBOs undergoing significant changes can be identified from a plot of the evolution of orbitals in going from the reactant to the product complex (Figure S6). The similar scenario exists for the reactions of both of the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complexes with the remaining substrates (Figure S7 and S8, respectively).

The analogies and differences between bidirectional H^-/e^- and OH^-/e^- reactions. A bidirectional OH^-/e^- mechanism is an established route for OH rebound reactions in (bio)inorganic systems.^[33-38] The off-diagonal thermodynamic-based contributions to the OH rebound activity were studied for a series of OH rebound reactions between the axially-substituted and tetramethylcyclam-supported (X)(TMC)Fe^{III}-OH complexes and cyclohexadiene.^[24] The study demonstrated the link between the reaction mechanism and a thermodynamic cycle with a more favorable off-diagonal contribution to the barrier. In parallel, it provided electronic structure descriptors capturing to the mechanism (as in eqs (4) and (5)).^[24] To gain a deeper understanding of the coupled OH^-/e^- transfer in relation to the presented HCET, we also explore here the evolution of IBOs during the reaction. Our findings support the bidirectional transfer of the OH^- fragment from Fe^{III}-OH to cyclohexadiene radical, alongside the concurrent transfer of an unpaired β π -electron from the radical to the Fe center (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6. The evolution of important IBOs in the OH^-/e^- mechanism for OH rebound reaction between $(CH_3CN)(TMC)Fe^{III}-OH$ complex and cyclohexadiene.

However, this OH rebound mechanism differs noticeably from the HCET mechanism observed in $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$. In the OH^-/e^- case, three electrons participate in the hydroxyl group transfer: two OH σ -electrons and one unpaired electron from cyclohexadiene radical. Unlike in the H^-/e^- mechanism, the electron transferred back is distinct from the ones initially transferred from the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complex. The OH^-/e^- transfer clearly resembles the reported concerted fluoride electron transfer by Xue and co-workers, where one electron is transferred from the boryl radical to the F-donor and two C-F σ -electrons are used to form a new B-F bond.^[39]

Since IBO analyses suggest hydroxide-coupled electron transfer to be classified as a three-electron transfer process, while hydride-coupled electron transfer is more accurately described as a two-electron transfer process, it may also explain why the Δq and ΔV descriptors from eqs (1) and (2), which are used to distinguish HCET from PCET, differ from the descriptors in eqs (3) and (4), which are employed to differentiate bidirectional OH^-/e^- from PCET-analogous unidirectional OH^\pm/e^- transfer. Here, we speculate that three-electron HCET is possible to exist provided hydride transfer is more spatially separated from electron transfer.

Conclusions

In this study, we investigated an alternative mechanism to proton-coupled electron transfer (PCET): hydride-coupled electron transfer (HCET), also described as a bidirectional H^-/e^- reaction. This mechanism was found to operate in the reaction between a $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ complex and various organic substrates, involving the transfer of a hydride between the reactants, coupled in a single step with electron transfer from $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ to the substrate. To distinguish between HCET and PCET mechanisms, we employed the concept of thermodynamic cycles along with a three-

component thermodynamic framework that directly links the energetics of off-diagonal states—namely, electron transfer (ET) and proton or hydride transfer (PT or HT) states — to the free energy barrier of the reaction. Recognizing that the accessibility of these off-diagonal states influences the reaction barrier, we proposed that the HCET mechanism operates due to a more favorable combination of thermodynamic frustration and asynchronicity effects on the reaction barrier. Given that HCET and PCET exhibit distinct off-diagonal states, this approach allowed us to identify HCET as the preferred mechanism in the $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ system. We further unambiguously linked the two distinct mechanisms to electronic structure-based descriptors derived from AIM charges and volumes. These descriptors revealed that the transferred hydrogen atom in HCET gains electron density and volume at the TS (partially adopting hydride character), whereas the hydrogen atom in PCET loses electron density and volume, exhibiting a proton character. This conclusion was further supported by analyzing electron flow along the reaction coordinate using intrinsic bond orbitals. The reaction between $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}$ and the donor follows conventional PCET mechanism, in which the proton and one C–H σ -electron are transferred independently to the Cu center, while the second σ -electron remains on the donor fragment. In contrast, the reaction involving $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ follows a distinct HCET mechanism, where both the proton and the C–H α -electron are fully transferred from substrate to the Cu ion. Meanwhile, the β -electron undergoes a temporary exchange, first moving to the Cu center before returning to substrate as the reaction progresses. This mechanism was further compared to the OH rebound pathway, which also involves bidirectional anion/electron transfer. However, the bidirectionality in each case differs: in HCET, it results from the complete transfer of one electron and the transient exchange of another, while in the OH rebound mechanism, three separate electrons are involved in the anion and electron transfer steps (**Scheme 1**).

Scheme 1. The modus operandi of the unidirectional $[H^{\pm}/e^{-}]$ mechanism (left) and the bidirectional $[X^{-}/e^{-}]$ mechanism in the presented hydride-coupled electron transfer (*middle*) and hydroxide-coupled electron transfer (*right*) from ref 24. The HCET can be classified as two-electron process contrasting to the latter featured as three-electron process.

Supporting Information

Computational details, Gibbs free energies of investigated species, thermodynamic and reactivity data for the substrates and $Cu^{III}-OH/Cu^{II}-OH$ complexes, scheme of oxidants and substrates used in the study, additional analysis of: performance of the three-component model and electronic-structure descriptors and changes intrinsic bond orbitals along the reaction coordinate. A data set collection of computational results (including transition state structures, reactant and product complexes).

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Table of Contents graphic

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